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Research Article

THE LABORATORY WASTE MANAGEMENT IN PHARMACY FIELD

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ABSTRACT

The management of pharmaceutical waste plays a significant role in pharmacy schools. Wastes are undesirable substances that can no longer be employed in manufacturing processes and may be eventually become substances that are harmful or not to humans or the environment. The management of hazardous wastes is a crucial component of pharmacy school. Pharmaceutical wastes come in a variety forms, primarily as organic waste or synthetic waste, testing waste, formulation waste, analytical waste, etc. It originates from a variety of departments within the colleges. The college manages these wastes with the aid of a waste management system. In this paper, we employ an alternative method for waste management.

Keywords: Waste products, pharmaceutical waste, Disposal methods.

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1. INTRODUCTION

There is a tonne of literature on disposal techniques for biomedical waste, but very little of it discusses liquid waste. According to the 2018 Government of India BMW rule, proper management of biomedical waste is required, lawful, and traceable. The typical neglect of liquid waste results in the unintentional release of contaminated liquid waste into the public drainage system. This could occasionally cause a significant public health issue. Utilizing a straightforward, inexpensive, and uncomplicated technique would encourage clinical laboratories and healthcare organisations to quickly accept and use this safe practise. The current essay focuses on one such effort to control contaminated liquid waste produced by small healthcare organisations and clinical diagnostic laboratories. For the disinfection of liquid, many disinfectant agents can be utilised. Drugs that are toxic or expired may also be disposed of in this liquid handling system after being treated with the proper chemicals. The building of a straightforward liquid waste management system for a pharmaceutical laboratory is the subject of this study. There are also many hazardous wastes comes out of the laboratory.[1]

As we all know that treating liquid waste is as important as treating other wastes. But not only treatment of water but also to reuse that liquid waste with the help of Green Chemistry. We studied many review and research papers for this purpose.

An essential goal in line with the National Environmental Policy is the reduction of pollutant emissions from research operations. As a result, the goal of this study is to collect both qualitative and quantitative data on hazardous waste, analyse the inventory of hazardous waste at NRC, create a guideline for managing hazardous waste, and finally, implement countermeasures to stop the discharge of hazardous waste into sewage and the surrounding environment. By supporting in the formulation and execution of environmental management programmes that adhere to crucial National regulatory standards and reduce pollution, this increased environmental performance.[2]

An active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) is a chemical component that has pharmacological action and a beneficial impact on the diagnosis, treatment, mitigation, or prevention of disease or one that changes the anatomy or physiology of the body. More than 20,000 parenteral, topical, and oral medication preparations contain small molecule APIs. These APIs eventually get up in marine ecosystems, sewage sludge and bio-solids, animal tissues, drinking water supplies, surface and ground waterways, and food chains. Both the abiotic and biotic systems are impacted by APIs. The use of drugs is growing daily in both the human and veterinary populations. One estimate puts the annual consumption of antimicrobials at 100,000 tonnes.[3]

Table 1: Laboratory waste streams' characteristics and related disposal techniques[4]

Waste stream	Example	Standard of disposal method	Current disposal method
Non-hazardous waste	• Weak acids and bases	• Weak acid and bases are diluted with large amounts of water and disposed of via the drain	• All non-hazardous liquid waste (e.g., weak acid and bases) is discharged to the sanitary sewer system with no treatment
	• Debris contaminated with low concentration of hazardous chemicals	• Any waste contaminated with trace levels of a poison or carcinogen should be collected for incineration	• All contaminated debris with trace levels of a poison or carcinogen is disposed of in municipal solid waste bins

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction and emolition waste (e.g. gravel and sand, concrete, asphalt) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction and demolition wastes, metals, broken glass, plastics, and textiles are collected in specially designed containers for recycling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction and demolition waste dumped in an area at the side of the civil faculty and then collected to transfer to landfills
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metals (e.g., steel, aluminium foils) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metals are collected for Sale
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broken glass 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broken glass, plastics, and textile are disposed of in municipal solid waste bins
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plastics 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Textiles 		
Hazardous wastes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong acids and bases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect strong acids and bases separately and neutralize one with the other. If additional acid or base is required, sulfuric or hydrochloric acids and sodium or magnesium hydroxide, respectively, can be used 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All hazardous liquid waste (e.g., strong acids and bases, oil waste, etc.) is discharged into the sanitary sewer system with no treatment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oil waste (e.g., hydraulic oil, lubricating oil, emulsion, refined petroleum-based products) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the acid or base is highly concentrated, first dilute it to a concentration below 10 % 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biohazardous wastes are disposed of in municipal solid waste bins or via the sanitary sewer with no treatment
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biohazardous waste (e.g., bacterial cultures, plant, and animal tissue) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All hazardous solid wastes (e.g., batteries) are disposed of in municipal solid waste bins
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy metals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oil waste should be collected in a proper waste container for recycling
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Batteries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste streams and equipment coming into contact with the biological products are collected in plastic bags and autoclaved for 15 min at 121 °C 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Batteries should be collected for recycling 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solvents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wastes containing heavy metals, explosives, oxidisers, toxic and 	

		poisons, carcinogenic should be disposed of according their MSDs (material safety data sheets)	
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2. Evaluation of Current Laboratory Waste Management:

Methodology Since an effective waste management requires a comprehensive understanding of current management systems, the methodology of the program focuses on the study of the current situation and investigation of major problems.

Evaluation of Current Waste Management Situation Prior to producing an integrated laboratory waste management, it is essential to evaluate current waste management and study its strong and weak points. Therefore, the next step of the study is dedicated to the evaluation of different waste management factors. A scoring system has been suggested in this chapter to compare the level of waste management in separate facilities. This system is based on the questionnaire which was filled in by laboratories' officers.[4]

Fig. 1: Classification of Laboratory Waste [5]

Wastewater treatment is an environmental friendly process as a control of water pollution. Many people have investigated the various wastewater treatment methods extensively on the national and international levels and much research tried to reduce the cost for recycling of the water.[6]

3. Steps to Follow When Testing Unknowns in a Lab:

When the identity of the item is unknown, straightforward in-lab test procedures can be utilised to determine the hazard class into which the material should be placed. Because the generator could be able to provide some general information, it might be preferable to carry out the test procedures before the materials are removed from the lab. Only conduct these tests if you can do so safely and only if doing so will enable you to classify the waste according to the guidelines provided by your hazardous waste disposal business. Be warned that the test methods indicated below are only meant to provide additional information; they do not satisfy the EPA's regulatory requirements for waste analysis. Before agreeing to handle unidentified materials, treatment and disposal facilities frequently need the following information:

1. physical characteristics,
2. water solubility,
3. ignitability (flammability),
4. water reactivity
5. Existence of an oxidizer,
6. the presence of sulphides or cyanides,
7. the presence of halogens,
8. Radioactive materials,
9. biohazardous materials,
10. poisonous components,
11. The presence of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs),
12. And compounds with a strong scent [7]

The major objective of the practise is to stop the degradation of water quality brought on by Institutional laboratory research:

Investigate the strengths and weaknesses of the current laboratory waste management system.

- To evaluate the danger potential of laboratory waste streams.
- Identify the primary causes of weak points in existing laboratory waste management.
- Determine whether or not laboratory waste streams can be recycled.
- Develop wastewater experiments and carry out the task of recovering heavy metals.
- Examine the effects of laboratory wastewater on diverse plants, particularly desert plants.
- Teach students about water analysis and instil in them a concern for the environment.[8]

Water stabilisation ponds are frequently utilised in tropical countries like Tanzania, Kenya, Malawi, Uganda, Zambia, Botswana, and Zimbabwe for the treatment of wastewater. Many of these systems have been operating and maintaining themselves improperly, which has caused them to function below the required standards. Constructed wetlands have not yet received the attention they deserve as an alternative to traditional wastewater treatment.⁹

4. Management of Laboratory Waste in the State of Khartoum:

Sharps and needle trash, biological waste primarily made up of human samples (urine, faeces, and blood), and routine garbage are present in the majority of medical laboratories in the state of Khartoum. Chemical waste, media, and radioactive waste, which is the least common waste, are listed below in that order. More than two thirds of the laboratory employees did not receive waste management training or workshops. The majority of laboratories have specialised businesses that have been authorised by authorities to collect and process medical waste. A similar percentage of laboratories employ a dustman for this purpose, and in a select minority, laboratory staff is responsible for garbage collection and treatment. The majority of laboratory employees separate medical sharps from other types of trash in safety boxes before disposing of it with a medical waste disposal business. Most laboratories reuse the safety box or bury or burn it instead of disposing of it in a landfill. Most

laboratory staff members lack the knowledge necessary to properly manage chemical waste. There are different disposal techniques for chemical and biological waste, as shown below: Lab waste in medical laboratories in the state of Khartoum occurs frequently:

Frequency-Number-Waste types:

- 91.7%-33-Needles and sharps
- 94.4%-34-Biological (patients' samples)
- 22.2%-8-Bacteria culture media
- 33.3%-12-Chemicals
- 8.3%-3-Radioactive
- 91.7%-33-house [10]

What If I Pour My Lab Waste Down the Drain?

When appropriately released to a sewer system and combined with residential sewage that will be treated in a publicly owned treatment works (POTW), wastes may occasionally be exempt from hazardous waste regulations (see OAC rule 3745-51-04(A) for details). Pouring hazardous material down the drain is prohibited in some situations, such as with D003 reactive cyanide wastewater (for details, see OAC rule 3745-270-03(B)). Additionally, you are prohibited from introducing specific wastes into a publicly owned treatment works (POTW) in accordance with OAC rule 3745-3-04(B). The list of wastes forbidden from discharge in this regulation includes:

1. *Contaminants that provide a risk of fire or explosion.*
2. *Contaminants that will harm the POTW's structure corrosively.*
3. *Pollutants that are solid or viscous and will block.*
4. *Any pollutant that has been discharged at a flow rate or concentration that interferes with the POTW.*
5. *Heat levels that prevent biological activity.*
6. *Fossil fuel.*
7. *Pollutants that cause harmful gases, vapours, or fumes to exist inside the POTW; and*
8. *Any pollutants transported (aside from at discharge points)[11]*

Recycling and Storage

Recycling-

Wastes that satisfy certain criteria may be sent for recycling on-site or off. For instance, some solvents can be cleaned up and used again to extract samples, while mercury can be recycled. Then, this trash is classed as a hazardous substance. This disposal method is difficult to carry out and frequently needs special permission from permitting authorities.

Storage-

Samples and sample trash may occasionally be returned to the point of origin for storage. Contacting the coordinator of the Environmental Protection Agency will be necessary for this return.[12]

Laboratory wastewater

The wastewater must be treated using coagulation or adsorption methods, or other ways, generally a mixed process, because it not only contains heavy metals but also, COD, BOD, TSS, TDS, and an unclear pH. Based on the findings of earlier tests and research, it was known that a pre-treatment and treatment process is necessary in accordance with the substance included in the wastewater to treat laboratory wastewater that meets the quality requirement set by the Ministry of Environment of RI.13

Non-hazardous biological waste

1. Ordinary municipal garbage (solid) or sewage (liquid) may be used to dispose of biological waste (Other than animal carcasses or body parts) that is not infectious or otherwise harmful to people, animals, plants, or the environment. Animal bodies and corpses must be burned or taken to a commercial rendering facility for processing.
2. Non-hazardous biological waste has no record keeping or labelling requirements.
3. All microbiological products should be autoclaved or cleaned in the laboratory. Bacterial or "normal" cell

cultures and original tissues should be autoclaved or treated with a 10% solution of sodium hypochlorite (Or an equivalent solution) before being used as culture materials or biological specimens. Waste that is liquid should be disposed of in the sewer system. Avoid situations that could lead to sight or smell issues.

4. Waste that is not harmful should not be labelled as such. Labelling containers with "NONHAZARDOUS LABORATORY WASTE" is required. Never use "red bags" or biohazard bags for non-hazardous garbage.
5. When possible, agricultural waste including manure, bedding, and another non-hazardous animal bedding should be used as compost or fertiliser. Reduce the number of recyclables deposited in the landfill.[14]

The literature study findings show that:

- Laboratory waste management needs to be taken into consideration because it has made the current state of waste management a cause for concern.
- The waste stream from laboratories has a significant amount of potential for hazards, such as strong acids and bases and reactive, explosive, flammable, oxidising, and poisonous compounds.
- 9A sizeable amount of garbage falls into the categories that are recyclable or may be recyclable (such as metals, construction, and demolition waste,
- oil waste, etc.).
- Implementing a pilot study under the guidance of a waste management specialist is another aspect of environmental efforts that are commonly addressed.

The pilot programme should include the following activities:

- Development of training courses and workshops for laboratory officers
- Diagnosis and inventory of waste produced

- Design of alternatives to eliminate or reduce the generation of laboratory waste
- Design of alternatives to separate hazardous/recyclable wastes and materials from the waste stream
- Provision of a laboratory waste management guideline for students.

Conclusion

The current study, the first of its sort in the relevant literature, set out to assess the overall pollutant load of laboratory effluent. For a month of observation, laboratory wastewater was examined. The study's findings revealed that laboratory wastewater's pH was bad for soil and was eroding its fertility. Additionally, it was discovered that heavy metal concentrations that might be harmful to human health was beyond the permitted levels. The studies revealed that the wastewater included significant amounts of pathogen organisms. Furthermore, even though viral pathogens were excluded from the investigation, we only looked at whether microbial growth occurred after applying an antibacterial polyherbal solution. The findings of the current investigation unequivocally showed that laboratory wastewater significantly increased the pollution load of the total college system.

Reference

1. Management of Liquid Waste in a Clinical Laboratory. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci*, 7(8), 4024-4028.
2. ABOU-ELELA, S. I., & IBRAHIM, H. (May 2019). MANAGEMENT OF LABORATORY HAZARDOUS WASTES: EXPERIENCE FROM EGYPT (10)
3. Kadam, A., Patil, S., Patil, S., & Tumkur, A. (2016). Pharmaceutical waste management an overview. *Indian Journal of Pharmacy Practice*, 9(1).
4. Yekkalar, M., Panahi, S., & Nikravan, M. (2015). Evaluation of current laboratory waste management: a step towards green campus at Amirkabir University of Technology. *Implementing Campus Greening Initiatives: Approaches, Methods, and Perspectives*, 215-227.
5. Akhtar, Malik Muhammad & Zhonghua, Tang & Dawood, Ammar & Sohail, Muhammad Tayyab. (2014). A Study to Investigate and Compare Groundwater Quality in Adjacent Areas of Landfill Sites in Lahore City. *Nature Environment and Pollution Technology*. 13. 1-10.
6. Jayashree, D., Arvind, C., & Sangita, I. (2014). Design of laboratory-based wastewater treatment plant. *Int. Res. J. of Science & Engineering*, 2(3), 104-111.
7. Prudent Practices in the Laboratory: Handling and Management of Chemical Hazards, Updated Version. (2011). United States: National Academies Press.
8. Amoatey, Peace & Bani, Richard. (2011). *Wastewater Management*. 21.
9. S. Phuntsho, H.K. Shon, S. Vigneswaran, and J. Kandasu, WATER AND WASTEWATER TREATMENT TECHNOLOGIES – Vol. II – Wastewater Stabilization Ponds (WSP) for Wastewater Treatment.
10. Hussein Abker Hussein (5th March 2021). Assessment of laboratory waste management and laboratory staff awareness in Khartoum state, (10).
11. Division of Environmental Response and Revitalization (October 2020). *Managing Hazardous Waste Generated in Laboratories*. (7)
12. Office of Research and Development (October 2010). *Laboratory Environmental Sample Disposal Information Document Companion to Standardized Analytical Methods for Environmental Restoration Following Homeland Security Events (SAM) – Revision 5.0*
13. Susila Arita, Tuty Emilia Agustina, Nurul Ilmi, Violanda Dwi Wulandari Pranajaya, Rianzya Gayatri (28 March 2022). Treatment of Laboratory Wastewater by Using Fenton Reagent and Combination of Coagulation-Adsorption as Pretreatment, 211-221.

14. Buck Shaw, Albert Lopez, Kimberlee Sandoval,
(April 1999). MANAGEMENT AND DISPOSAL OF
BIOLOGICAL WASTE AT TEXAS A&M
INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY (16).